

A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON JOB SATISFACTION, WORK COMMITMENT, AND WORK-LIFE BALANCE AMONG EMPLOYEES IN THE FAST-FOOD INDUSTRY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20304281>

ABSTRACT

This study examined the levels of job satisfaction, work commitment, and work-life balance among employees of fast-food establishments in Dipolog City, including their relationships and differences when grouped according to selected profile variables. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed, with data collected from 200 respondents using a structured questionnaire. Statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, mean, Mann–Whitney U test, Kruskal–Wallis H test, and Spearman rank correlation were utilized to analyze the data at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that employees were generally satisfied with their jobs, with relatedness needs obtaining the highest rating, followed by existence needs, while growth needs ranked lowest. Employees demonstrated a moderate level of work commitment, with affective commitment emerging as the strongest dimension. In terms of work-life balance, respondents experienced a moderate level of work-life conflict, indicating that job demands and family responsibilities tend to interfere with one another. Significant differences in job satisfaction and work motivation were observed when respondents were grouped according to age, tenure status, and position, while work-life balance differed only in terms of tenure status. Further analysis revealed a strong positive relationship between job satisfaction and work commitment, a moderate positive relationship between work-life balance and job satisfaction, and a weak but significant relationship between work-life balance and work commitment. These findings underscore the critical role of organizational and work-related factors in shaping employees' attitudes and behaviors. The study recommends strengthening compensation, employee

development programs, workplace support systems, and work-life balance policies to enhance employee satisfaction, commitment, and overall well-being.

Keywords: *Job Satisfaction, Work Commitment, Work-Life Balance, Fast-Food Employees, Organizational Factors, Dipolog City*

INTRODUCTION

The fast-food sector in the Philippines had emerged as one of the most rapidly expanding segments of the service economy, driven by urbanization, changing consumer lifestyles, and the growing demand for convenience. As fast-food establishments continued to expand across both metropolitan and provincial areas, they created employment opportunities, particularly for young and entry-level workers (Gumasing, 2025). However, alongside this growth came increasing human resource challenges. Employees in this sector were frequently exposed to demanding work conditions, including irregular schedules, extended working hours, high-pressure service demands, and continuous customer interaction. Such conditions significantly influenced employees' job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and work-life balance—key determinants of both individual well-being and organizational performance (Castor et al., 2025).

Extant foreign literature underscored the critical role of job satisfaction, work commitment, and work-life balance in shaping employee behavior and organizational outcomes. Job satisfaction had been consistently linked to enhanced performance, reduced turnover intentions, and stronger organizational loyalty (Baxi & Astre, 2024). Similarly, organizational commitment—particularly affective commitment—had been identified as a crucial predictor of employee retention and sustained engagement. Work-life balance, on the other hand, was widely recognized as essential in mitigating stress, preventing burnout, and promoting overall well-being, especially in high-demand service industries (Soliman, 2023). These studies further highlighted the effectiveness of structured human resource practices, such as flexible scheduling, employee support programs, and leadership development, in fostering positive employee outcomes.

In the Philippine context, local studies affirmed these relationships but situated them within distinct socio-economic and cultural conditions. Research in the food service and hospitality sectors indicated that job satisfaction significantly influenced organizational commitment, both of which were shaped by workplace conditions, compensation, and management practices (Cao & Deeprasert, 2024). Moreover, work-life balance remained a persistent concern among Filipino employees due to long working hours, shifting schedules, and strong family-oriented cultural expectations. Organizational climate—particularly fairness, supervision, and interpersonal relationships—had likewise been identified as a critical determinant of employee satisfaction and retention in local settings (Nuñez & Guballo, 2025).

Despite these similarities, notable differences existed between foreign and local literature. Foreign studies on quick-service restaurants (QSRs) typically emphasized structured organizational systems and formal human resource interventions, including training programs, standardized reward systems, and leadership development initiatives. These frameworks had been shown to enhance job satisfaction and organizational commitment through motivation, recognition, and organizational support (Chan et al., 2024; AlKahtani et al., 2021). In contrast, local studies often reflected contextual realities such as limited career advancement opportunities, modest wages, and socio-cultural expectations that shaped employee attitudes and experiences. For instance, studies conducted in Davao and similar settings revealed that job characteristics and workplace conditions strongly influenced employee satisfaction and commitment within environments characterized by high turnover and limited resources (Olivar et al., 2023; Jiang & Po, 2023). Furthermore, local research emphasized the role of organizational culture, interpersonal relationships, and value alignment in sustaining employee satisfaction despite structural constraints (Chico et al., 2023; Plata et al., 2020).

Notably, both foreign and local studies tended to examine job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and work-life balance in isolation or through limited pairwise relationships. While some research explored job satisfaction as a predictor of employee retention and others focused on organizational commitment in relation to turnover intentions or operational outcomes (Alserhan et al., 2020; Rodriguez & Palallos, 2024), few studies investigated the combined and interactive effects of these variables within a unified framework. This limitation highlighted a significant gap in the literature, particularly within the food service industry, where complex work environments necessitated a more integrated understanding of employee experiences.

In the context of Dipolog City, fast-food employees played a vital role in the local economy but encountered unique challenges, including limited employment opportunities, entry-level job structures, and demanding work conditions. Although certain employee benefits were provided, their actual implementation and impact on employee well-being remained unclear. Additionally, rotating shifts and strong family expectations may have further complicated employees' ability to maintain a healthy work-life balance.

Given these considerations, there was a clear need for localized, integrative, and comparative research that examined the interrelationship among job satisfaction, work commitment, and work-life balance in provincial settings. While foreign literature provided robust evidence within structured environments and local studies validated these constructs in the Philippine context, there remained a scarcity of research that bridged these perspectives and explored how these variables interacted collectively in smaller cities such as Dipolog City. Existing studies also failed to determine whether patterns observed in urban and international contexts were applicable to provincial environments characterized by distinct socio-economic and cultural dynamics (Bolongan & Chavez, 2025; Nuñez & Guballo, 2025; Heniel, 2024; Macalinao, 2023).

Addressing this gap was essential to generate context-specific insights that reflected the lived realities of fast-food employees in Dipolog City. Hence, this study aimed to examine the interrelationship among job satisfaction, work commitment, and work-life balance, thereby providing a more comprehensive understanding of employee experiences and contributing to the development of responsive and effective human resource practices in the Philippine service industry during the year 2026.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the interrelationship of job satisfaction, work commitment, and work-life balance among fast-food employees in Dipolog City for the year 2026.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Gender;
 - 1.3. Marital Status;
 - 1.4. Educational Attainment;
 - 1.5. Tenure Status;
 - 1.6. Position; and
 - 1.7. Number of Years Working in the Organization?
2. What is the level of job satisfaction among employees of fast food establishments in Dipolog City, as to:
 - 2.1. Existence;
 - 2.2. Relatedness; and
 - 2.3. Growth?
3. What is the level of work commitment among employees of fast food establishments in Dipolog City, as to:
 - 3.1. Affective;
 - 3.2. Continuance; and
 - 3.3. Normative?
4. What is the level of work-life balance among the employees in terms of:
 - 4.1. work to family conflict; and
 - 4.2. family to work conflict?
5. Is there a significant difference on the level of job satisfaction among employees of fast-food employees when analyzed according to their profile?
6. Is there a significant difference on the level of work commitment among employees of fast-food employees when analyzed according to their profile?
7. Is there a significant difference on the level of work-life balance among employees of fast-food employees when analyzed according to their profile?
8. Is there a significant relationship between job satisfaction and work commitment among employees of fast-food establishments?
9. Is there a significant relationship between job satisfaction and work-life balance among employees of fast-food establishments?

10. Is there a significant relationship between work commitment and work-life balance among employees of fast-food establishments?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive research design to systematically examine the interrelationship among job satisfaction, work commitment, and work-life balance among fast-food employees in Dipolog City. A structured, self-developed questionnaire was used as the primary data collection instrument, consisting of four sections: respondents' demographic profile, job satisfaction, work commitment (affective, continuance, and normative), and work-life balance (work–family and family–work conflict).

The study was conducted in Dipolog City, a growing urban center in Zamboanga del Norte with an expanding fast-food industry composed of both national and local establishments. A total of 201 respondents were selected from a population of 417 employees using Cochran's sampling formula, ensuring adequate representation. However, only 200 respondents responded positively and completely participated in the study. Participants were required to meet specific inclusion criteria, including being at least 18 years old, currently employed in selected establishments, having at least three months of work experience, and providing voluntary informed consent.

The research instrument underwent content validation by experts and pilot testing in Dapitan City. Reliability was established using Cronbach's alpha, which indicated acceptable internal consistency. Data were gathered through on-site distribution of questionnaires during respondents' free time to avoid disruption of work duties.

Ethical standards were strictly observed, including obtaining permission from establishments, ensuring voluntary participation, maintaining anonymity and confidentiality, and securing informed consent. Data were used solely for academic purposes and handled with strict data protection measures.

For data analysis, frequency and percentage were used to describe respondents' profiles, while weighted mean assessed levels of job satisfaction, work commitment, and work-life balance. The ANOVA F-test, Mann–Whitney U-test and Kruskal–Wallis H- test determined differences across groups, and Spearman rank-order correlation was used to examine relationships among variables. All analyses were performed using SPSS at a 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results and corresponding discussions of the present investigation. The data gathered were statistically treated to address and answer the research questions of the study.

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, marital status, educational attainment, tenure status, position, and number of years working in the organization. The data reveal that the majority of the respondents belonged to the 18–27 years old age group, with 106 respondents (53.00%), followed by those aged 28–37 years old, with 78 respondents (39.00%). Only a small proportion belonged to older age brackets, with 15 respondents (7.50%) aged 38–47 years old and 1 respondent (0.50%) aged 48–57 years old. No respondents were aged 58 years old and above. These findings indicate that the fast-food workforce is largely composed of young adults, reflecting the industry’s reliance on a youthful labor force. This result supports the findings of Santos (2025) and Macalinao (2023), who reported that fast-food establishments are predominantly staffed by young and entry-level employees due to the physically demanding and flexible nature of the work. Younger employees are also more likely to prioritize flexibility, career growth, and work-life balance, which are common characteristics associated with service-oriented industries.

In terms of gender, the majority of the respondents were female, with 111 respondents (55.50%), while 89 respondents (44.50%) were male. This indicates that female employees slightly outnumber male employees in the fast-food sector within the study area. The result suggests that women continue to dominate service-oriented roles that require customer interaction, communication, and interpersonal skills. Jaxel (2024) similarly emphasized that women are increasingly concentrated in hospitality and food-service industries due to the service-centered demands of these occupations.

With respect to marital status, the majority of the respondents were single, with 124 respondents (62.00%), followed by married respondents, with 71 (35.50%). Only 5 respondents (2.50%) were separated, while none were widow/widower. These findings suggest that the fast-food workforce is largely composed of unmarried individuals, which is consistent with the predominance of younger employees in the industry. The Philippine Statistics Authority (2023) reported that service-sector jobs are often occupied by young and unmarried workers because they are more flexible and adaptable to irregular working schedules commonly found in fast-food establishments.

In terms of educational attainment, the largest group consisted of college-level respondents, with 84 respondents (42.00%), followed closely by degree holders, with 79 respondents (39.50%). Meanwhile, 22 respondents (11.00%) were high school level or graduates, 9 respondents (4.50%) were elementary level or graduates, and 6 respondents (3.00%) were vocational or diploma graduates. No respondents had masteral or doctoral degrees. These findings indicate that most employees possess at least some level of higher education, suggesting that fast-food employment attracts students, recent graduates, and degree holders seeking work experience or temporary employment opportunities. German et al. (2024) and Centeno et al. (2024) similarly found that fast-food establishments are largely composed of college-level students and degree holders because the industry provides accessible entry-level employment opportunities.

As to tenure status, the majority of the respondents were regular or permanent employees, with 136 respondents (68.00%), followed by casual employees, with 62 respondents (31.00%), and seasonal employees, with only 2 respondents (1.00%). This implies that while fast-food establishments maintain a stable workforce through regular employment, they also utilize casual and seasonal workers to meet operational demands and fluctuating customer volume. Bareño et al. (2022) emphasized that service-sector establishments rely on both regular and non-regular employment arrangements to maintain operational flexibility and service efficiency.

Regarding position, the majority of the respondents were rank-and-file employees assigned in front service operations, with 148 respondents (74.00%). This was followed by managerial employees, with 42 respondents (21.00%), and supervisors, with only 10 respondents (5.00%). These findings indicate that fast-food establishments are heavily dependent on frontline workers who directly interact with customers and handle daily operations. Centeno et al. (2024) and Kumolu-Johnson (2024) explained that fast-food organizations commonly follow a hierarchical structure where a limited number of supervisors and managers oversee a larger base of operational personnel to ensure service quality and efficiency.

Lastly, in terms of number of years working in the organization, the majority of the respondents had rendered 0–5 years of service, with 150 respondents (75.00%). This was followed by 6–10 years, with 30 respondents (15.00%), 11–15 years, with 17 respondents (8.50%), and 16–20 years, with only 3 respondents (1.50%). No respondents had 21 years and above of service. These findings indicate that most employees have relatively short tenure in the organization, reflecting the high turnover and transitional nature of fast-food employment. Campos and Campos (2024), German et al. (2024), and Centeno et al. (2024) similarly found that fast-food establishments experience high employee turnover due to demanding work conditions and limited career advancement opportunities, causing many employees to treat fast-food work as temporary employment.

Table 1
Profile of the Respondents

Profile Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	18–27 years old	106	53.00
	28–37 years old	78	39.00
	38–47 years old	15	7.50
	48–57 years old	1	0.50
	58 years old and above	-	-
Total		200	100.00
Gender	Male	89	44.50
	Female	111	55.50

Profile Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
	Total	200	100.00
Marital Status	Single	124	62.00
	Married	71	35.50
	Separated	5	2.50
	Widow/Widower	-	-
	Total	200	100.00
Educational Attainment	Elementary Level/Graduate	9	4.50
	High School Level/Graduate	22	11.00
	College Level	84	42.00
	Vocational/Diploma Graduate	6	3.00
	Degree Holder	79	39.50
	Masteral/Doctoral	-	-
	Total	200	100.00
Tenure Status	Regular/Permanent Employee	136	68.00
	Casual Employee	62	31.00
	Seasonal Employee	2	1.00
	Total	200	100.00
Position	Rank and File (Front Service)	148	74.00
	Supervisor	10	5.00
	Managerial	42	21.00
	Total	200	100.00
Number of Years Working in the Organization	0–5 years	150	75.00
	6–10 years	30	15.00
	11–15 years	17	8.50
	16–20 years	3	1.50
	21 years and above	-	-
	Total	200	100.00

Table 2*Level of Job Satisfaction Among Employees of Fast-Food Establishments in Dipolog City*

Dimensions and Indicators	AWV	Verbal Description
Existence		
Receives salary that compensates needs	3.43	Highly Satisfied
Receives allowance fairly	3.03	Satisfied
Bonuses are received regularly	3.14	Satisfied
Receives standardized commission	2.54	Satisfied
Avails salary loan based on period of service rendered	2.99	Satisfied
Mean	3.02	Satisfied
Relatedness		
Schedule team building events to employees	3.07	Satisfied
Calls for monthly meetings to talk about company culture and other work-related discussions	3.25	Satisfied
Receives support from supervisors and co-employees when job is stressful and demanding	3.23	Satisfied
Feels love, affection, and sense of belongingness from co-employees, supervisors, and bosses	3.22	Satisfied
Recognizes employees' job well-done monthly/annually	3.17	Satisfied
Mean	3.19	Satisfied
Growth		
Offers educational grants to worthy employees	2.80	Satisfied
Motivates employees for promotion	2.86	Satisfied
Offers leave for employees to develop skills/expertise and learning	2.80	Satisfied
Attends seminars and trainings funded by the company	2.67	Satisfied
Gives chance to learn new skills and develop talents in the establishment	3.08	Satisfied
Mean	2.85	Satisfied
Grand Mean	3.02	Satisfied

Note. AWV = Average Weighted Value. Legend: 1.00–1.75 = Not Satisfied; 1.76–2.50 = Less Satisfied; 2.51–3.25 = Satisfied; 3.26–4.00 = Highly Satisfied.

Table 2 presents the level of job satisfaction among employees of fast-food establishments in Dipolog City in terms of existence, relatedness, and growth needs. The data reveal a grand mean of 3.02, interpreted as *Satisfied*, indicating that employees are generally satisfied with their jobs across all dimensions. Among the three dimensions, relatedness obtained the highest mean of 3.19 (*Satisfied*), suggesting that employees

experience positive interpersonal relationships, support, and a sense of belongingness within the workplace. This is followed by existence, with a mean of 3.02 (*Satisfied*), indicating that employees are generally content with their salaries, allowances, and financial benefits. On the other hand, growth recorded the lowest mean of 2.85 (*Satisfied*), implying that while employees are satisfied with opportunities for personal and professional development, such opportunities are only moderately experienced.

Specifically, under the existence dimension, the highest-rated indicator was “receives salary that compensates needs” with an average weighted value of 3.43 (*Highly Satisfied*), suggesting that employees perceive their salary as adequate in meeting their basic needs. Other indicators such as receiving bonuses regularly (3.14), receiving allowance fairly (3.03), and availing salary loans based on period of service rendered (2.99) were all interpreted as *Satisfied*. Meanwhile, “receives standardized commission” obtained the lowest mean of 2.54, although still verbally interpreted as *Satisfied*. These findings indicate that employees are generally content with the material and financial aspects of their work, although some benefit-related aspects still require improvement. Santos (2025) similarly noted that compensation-related factors such as commissions and benefits often receive lower satisfaction ratings compared to salary.

In terms of relatedness, the findings indicate that employees generally experience positive relationships and support within the organization. The highest-rated indicator was “calls for monthly meeting to talk about company culture and other work-related discussions” with a mean of 3.25 (*Satisfied*), followed by “receives support from supervisors and co-employees when job is stressful and demanding” (3.23) and “feels love, affection and sense of belongingness from co-employees, supervisors and bosses” (3.22). Other indicators such as recognizing employees’ job well-done monthly or annually (3.17) and scheduling team-building events (3.07) were likewise interpreted as *Satisfied*. These findings suggest that employees value effective communication, supervisory support, and teamwork, which contribute to a supportive organizational climate. Chico et al. (2023) emphasized that positive interpersonal relationships and recognition practices significantly contribute to employee satisfaction and performance in the fast-food industry.

Regarding the growth dimension, the findings reveal that employees are moderately satisfied with opportunities for career and professional development. The highest-rated indicator was “gives chance to learn new skills and develop talents in the establishment” with a mean of 3.08 (*Satisfied*), suggesting that employees recognize opportunities for skill enhancement in the workplace. This was followed by “motivates employees for promotions” (2.86), while “offers educational grants to worthy employees” (2.80) and “offers leave for employees to develop skills/expertise and learning” (2.80) were also interpreted as *Satisfied*. The lowest-rated indicator was “attends seminars and trainings funded by the company” with a mean of 2.67 (*Satisfied*), implying that formal training opportunities may not be consistently experienced by employees. The findings indicate that while employees appreciate growth-related opportunities, there is still a need

to strengthen training programs, career advancement initiatives, and professional development support. Bulalacao and Repatacodo (2025) similarly emphasized that growth opportunities in fast-food establishments require enhancement to improve employee development and long-term satisfaction.

The findings indicate that employees of fast-food establishments are generally satisfied across all dimensions of job satisfaction, particularly in terms of interpersonal relationships and workplace support. However, growth-related opportunities remain the weakest dimension, highlighting the need for continuous improvement in employee training, career advancement, and development programs. Molina et al. (2025) likewise emphasized that supportive workplace relationships significantly improve employee satisfaction, while growth-related opportunities require further strengthening to sustain employee engagement and performance.

Table 3

Level of Work Commitment Among Employees of Fast-Food Establishments in Dipolog City

Dimensions and Indicators	AWV	Verbal Description
Affective Commitment		
Feels a great deal of personal meaning with the establishment	3.20	Committed
Feels happy to spend the rest of career in this establishment	3.17	Committed
Develops a strong sense of belongingness to this establishment	3.13	Committed
Feels emotionally attached in this establishment	2.93	Committed
Develops a strong sense of ownership in the sense that the establishment problems are like my own	3.01	Committed
Mean	3.08	Committed
Continuance Commitment		
Finds it hard to leave this establishment because of attractive benefits	2.96	Committed
Stays with this establishment for security reasons	2.81	Committed
Continue to work due to familiarity with the organization	2.93	Committed
Stays with the establishment for economic reasons and lack of available alternatives	2.91	Committed
Remains in the establishment for personal investment like retirement plan, SSS contribution, and health insurance benefits	3.05	Committed
Mean	2.93	Committed
Normative Commitment		
Stays loyal with the establishment because of feeling of responsibility to work	3.17	Committed

Dimensions and Indicators	AWV	Verbal Description
Stays with the establishment because of sense of obligation to the guests and co-employees	2.88	Committed
Feels indebted with the establishment especially in difficult times	2.76	Committed
Develops the feeling of “ought to stay” in the establishment because of gratitude to bosses, supervisors, and co-employees	2.98	Committed
Feels guilty if leaving this establishment	2.74	Committed
Mean	2.90	Committed
Grand Mean	2.97	Committed

Note. AWV = Average Weighted Value. Legend: 1.00–1.75 = Not Committed; 1.76–2.50 = Less Committed; 2.51–3.25 = Committed; 3.26–4.00 = Highly Committed.

Table 3 presents the level of work commitment among employees of fast-food establishments in Dipolog City in terms of affective, continuance, and normative commitment. The data reveal a grand mean of 2.97, interpreted as *Committed*, indicating that employees generally demonstrate a positive level of commitment to their organization. Among the three dimensions, affective commitment obtained the highest mean of 3.08 (*Committed*), suggesting that employees possess a stronger emotional attachment, sense of belongingness, and identification with the organization. This is followed by continuance commitment, with a mean of 2.93 (*Committed*), indicating that employees remain in the organization due to practical considerations such as job security, benefits, and personal investments. Meanwhile, normative commitment recorded the lowest mean of 2.90 (*Committed*), implying that although employees feel a sense of obligation and responsibility to stay, this aspect is slightly less emphasized compared to the other dimensions.

Specifically, under affective commitment, the highest-rated indicator was “feels a great deal of personal meaning with the establishment” with an average weighted value of 3.20 (*Committed*), suggesting that employees find significance and purpose in their work. This was followed by “feels happy to spend the rest of career in this establishment” (3.17) and “develops a strong sense of belongingness to this establishment” (3.13), both interpreted as *Committed*, reflecting employees’ emotional connection and organizational identification. Meanwhile, “develops a strong sense of ownership in the sense that the establishment problems are like my own” (3.01) and “feels emotionally attached in this establishment” (2.93) were also interpreted as *Committed*, although slightly lower, indicating varying levels of emotional attachment among employees. The findings imply that employees demonstrate a moderate level of emotional commitment characterized by meaning, belongingness, and attachment to the organization. Nuñez and Guballo (2025) and Heniel (2024) similarly found that employees in Philippine service sectors exhibit affective commitment through emotional attachment and organizational belongingness.

In terms of continuance commitment, the findings indicate that employees remain in the organization primarily because of practical and economic considerations. The highest-rated indicator was “remains in the establishment for personal investment like retirement plan, SSS contribution and health insurance benefits” with a mean of 3.05 (*Committed*), suggesting that employees value employment-related benefits and investments. This was followed by “finds it hard to leave this establishment because of attractive benefits” (2.96) and “continue to work due to familiarity with the organization” (2.93), both interpreted as *Committed*. Other indicators such as “stays with the establishment for economic reasons and lack of available alternatives” (2.91) and “stays with this establishment for security reasons” (2.81) also received a verbal interpretation of *Committed*. These findings suggest that employees’ decision to stay in the organization is influenced largely by economic stability, security, and accumulated benefits rather than solely emotional attachment. Gimeno et al. (2025) and Marpuri (2025) emphasized that employees often remain in organizations due to salary, benefits, and job security, highlighting the role of practical considerations in sustaining commitment.

Regarding normative commitment, the findings reveal that employees remain in the organization because of a sense of obligation, loyalty, and responsibility. The highest-rated indicator was “stays loyal with the establishment because of my feeling of responsibility to work” with a mean of 3.17 (*Committed*), suggesting that employees feel morally responsible to remain loyal to the organization. This was followed by “develops the feeling of ‘ought to stay’ in the establishment because of gratitude to my bosses, supervisors and co-employees” (2.98) and “stays with the establishment because of the sense of obligation to the guests and my co-employees” (2.88), both interpreted as *Committed*. Meanwhile, “feels indebted with the establishment especially in this difficult time” (2.76) and “feels guilty if I left this establishment” (2.74) were also rated as *Committed*, although comparatively lower. These findings suggest that employees demonstrate a moderate sense of loyalty and obligation toward the organization, influenced by interpersonal relationships and workplace culture. Bantilan et al. (2024) similarly emphasized that normative commitment among Filipino employees is shaped by responsibility, loyalty, gratitude, and interpersonal relationships within the workplace.

The findings indicate that employees are committed across all dimensions of work commitment, with affective commitment emerging as the strongest factor, followed by continuance and normative commitment. This implies that employees remain committed not only because of economic and practical reasons but also because of emotional attachment and social responsibility toward the organization. Mejia (2025) further emphasized that emotional attachment plays a greater role in employee commitment compared to economic or moral reasons, while strengthening organizational support, employee engagement, and development opportunities can further enhance long-term organizational commitment.

Table 4

Level of Work–Life Balance Among Employees of Fast-Food Establishments in Dipolog City

Dimensions and Indicators	AWV	Verbal Description
Work-to-Family Conflict		
I felt tired after work that I do not have time for my family	3.13	Agree
The stress that I had at work makes me irritable at home	2.60	Agree
I do not have personal time as I carry my work at home	2.71	Agree
The physical effect at work makes me go to sleep early at home	3.02	Agree
I felt lazy doing household chores as I want to feel relaxed at home when I am from work	2.90	Agree
Mean	2.87	Agree
Family-to-Work Conflict		
I leave my work at work when I am at home	3.06	Agree
I focus my time and energy at home and never accept any calls from work	2.68	Agree
I see to it that I had time at home so I had to balance my work time and home time	3.00	Agree
I do not accept overtime, unless necessary, so that I can have personal and family time	2.69	Agree
I comply my work on time so that it will not encroach my personal time	3.01	Agree
Mean	2.89	Agree
Grand Mean	2.88	Agree

Note. AWV = Average Weighted Value. Legend: 1.00–1.75 = Strongly Disagree; 1.76–2.50 = Disagree; 2.51–3.25 = Agree; 3.26–4.00 = Strongly Agree.

Table 4 presents the level of work–life balance among employees of fast-food establishments in Dipolog City in terms of work-to-family conflict and family-to-work conflict. The data reveal a grand mean of 2.88, interpreted as *Agree*, indicating that employees generally experience a moderate level of work–life conflict. Between the two dimensions, family-to-work conflict obtained a slightly higher mean of 2.89 (*Agree*) compared to work-to-family conflict with a mean of 2.87 (*Agree*), suggesting that both work and family responsibilities somewhat interfere with each other, although the difference is minimal. The findings imply that employees experience moderate work–life imbalance where job demands and family responsibilities affect one another, highlighting the need for supportive workplace practices and policies to help employees manage their responsibilities and improve overall well-being.

Specifically, under work-to-family conflict, the highest-rated indicator was “I felt tired after work that I do not have time for my family” with an average weighted value of 3.13 (*Agree*), suggesting that fatigue from work limits employees’ participation in family activities. This was followed by “the physical effect at work makes me go to sleep early at home” (3.02), indicating that the physical demands of work affect employees’ personal time and energy at home. Other indicators such as “I felt lazy doing household chores as I want to feel relaxed at home when I am from work” (2.90), “I do not have personal time as I carry my work at home” (2.71), and “the stress that I had at work makes me irritable at home” (2.60) were likewise interpreted as *Agree*. These findings indicate that work-related stress, fatigue, and physical exhaustion spill over into employees’ personal and family life, resulting in moderate work-to-family conflict. Campos and Campos (2024) similarly emphasized that demanding workloads and stressful work conditions in service-oriented industries contribute significantly to reduced work–life balance and increased work-to-family conflict.

In terms of family-to-work conflict, the findings indicate that employees attempt to manage family responsibilities in ways that minimally interfere with their work. The highest-rated indicator was “I leave my work at work when I am at home” with a mean of 3.06 (*Agree*), suggesting that employees try to establish boundaries between work and home life. This was followed by “I comply my work on time so that it will not encroach my personal time” (3.01) and “I see to it that I had time at home so I had to balance my work time and home time” (3.00), indicating efforts to balance work and family responsibilities effectively. Meanwhile, “I do not accept overtime, unless necessary, so that I can have personal and family time” (2.69) and “I focus my time and energy at home and never accept any calls from work” (2.68) were also rated as *Agree*, reflecting employees’ efforts to protect personal and family time despite work demands. These findings suggest that while employees actively attempt to balance family and work responsibilities, complete separation between the two domains remains difficult due to the demanding nature of the fast-food industry. Campos and Campos (2024) further highlighted that employees in service-oriented industries commonly struggle to fully separate work and family roles because of work-related stress and demanding schedules.

The findings indicate that employees of fast-food establishments experience moderate levels of work–life conflict across both dimensions. While employees make efforts to maintain balance between work and family responsibilities, the physically demanding and stressful nature of fast-food work continues to create challenges in achieving complete work–life balance. Tuliao (2025) similarly emphasized that food service employees in the Philippines often experience work–life imbalance due to long working hours, demanding workloads, and workplace stress, underscoring the importance of flexible scheduling, supportive organizational practices, and employee support programs to improve employee well-being and work–life balance.

Table 5

Test of Significant Difference on the Level of Job Satisfaction Among Employees of Fast-Food Establishments in Dipolog City When Analyzed According to Profile Variables

Profile Variables	Test Statistic	Computed Value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Age	F-value	35.4518	9.995×10^{-8}	Reject Ho	Significant Difference
Gender	U-value	4321	0.1283	Accept Ho	No Significant Difference
Marital Status	H-value	2.1047	0.3491	Accept Ho	No Significant Difference
Educational Attainment	F-value	3.1395	0.5348	Accept Ho	No Significant Difference
Tenure Status	H-value	46.2144	9.219×10^{-11}	Reject Ho	Significant Difference
Position	H-value	29.3054	4.33×10^{-7}	Reject Ho	Significant Difference
Number of Years Working in the Organization	H-value	17.4048	0.0005834	Reject Ho	Significant Difference

Note. Significant at 0.05 level of significance. If p-value is less than 0.05, reject Ho; if p-value is greater than 0.05, accept Ho.

Table 5 presents the test of significant difference on the level of job satisfaction among employees of fast-food establishments in Dipolog City when analyzed according to their profile variables. The results reveal that age has a significant difference in job satisfaction, as indicated by an F-value of 35.4518 and a p-value of 9.995×10^{-8} , which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Similarly, tenure status ($H = 46.2144$, $p = 9.219 \times 10^{-11}$), position ($H = 29.3054$, $p = 4.33 \times 10^{-7}$), and number of years working in the organization ($H = 17.4048$, $p = 0.0005834$) also show significant differences, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis for these variables. These findings imply that job satisfaction varies according to employees' age, employment status, job position, and length of service.

On the other hand, gender ($U = 4321$, $p = 0.1283$), marital status ($H = 2.1047$, $p = 0.3491$), and educational attainment ($F = 3.1395$, $p = 0.5348$) show no significant difference, as their p-values are greater than 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted for these variables, indicating that job satisfaction does not significantly differ based on gender, marital status, or educational attainment. These findings suggest that work-related and experiential factors, such as tenure, position, length of service, and age, significantly influence employees' job satisfaction, while personal demographic characteristics do not.

The findings pointed to the importance of organizational and experiential variables in shaping satisfaction levels among fast-food employees. Employees who differ in age, job status, organizational role, and years of service may have varying expectations, responsibilities, and workplace experiences, which influence their level of satisfaction. This result is supported by Almirante et al. (2025), who found that job satisfaction varies according to employment-related factors such as tenure, job position, and work experience. Their study emphasized that organizational conditions, compensation, and promotion opportunities are important predictors of satisfaction among fast-food employees. Similarly, Nuñez and Guballo (2025) reported that job satisfaction in the Philippine fast-food sector is largely influenced by work-related and experiential factors rather than demographic characteristics. They further noted that tenure, job role, and organizational environment significantly shape employees' perceptions and attitudes toward their work, while variables such as gender and marital status have minimal influence. These findings confirm that improving workplace conditions, employee support systems, and career development opportunities is essential in enhancing employees' job satisfaction.

Table 6
Test of Significant Difference on the Level of Work Motivation Among Employees of Fast-Food Establishments in Dipolog City When Analyzed According to Profile Variables

Profile Variables	Test Statistic	Computed Value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Age	F-value	19.760	0.0001907	Reject Ho	Significant Difference
Gender	U-value	4336	0.1377	Accept Ho	No Significant Difference
Marital Status	H-value	3.2325	0.5515	Accept Ho	No Significant Difference
Educational Attainment	F-value	7.288	0.1872	Accept Ho	No Significant Difference
Tenure Status	H-value	49.455	1.824×10^{-11}	Reject Ho	Significant Difference
Position	H-value	13.908	0.0009548	Reject Ho	Significant Difference
Number of Years Working in the Organization	H-value	6.1444	0.1048	Accept Ho	No Significant Difference

Note. Significant at 0.05 level of significance. If p-value is less than 0.05, reject Ho; if p-value is greater than 0.05, accept Ho.

Table 6 presents the test of significant difference on the level of work motivation among employees of fast-food establishments in Dipolog City when analyzed according to their profile variables. The results reveal that age has a significant difference in work

motivation, as indicated by an F-value of 19.760 and a p-value of 0.0001907, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Similarly, tenure status ($H = 49.455$, $p = 1.824 \times 10^{-11}$) and position ($H = 13.908$, $p = 0.0009548$) also show significant differences, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis for these variables. These findings imply that employees' work motivation varies according to their age, employment status, and organizational position. This suggests that work-related and experiential factors significantly influence employees' level of motivation in the workplace.

On the other hand, gender ($U = 4336$, $p = 0.1377$), marital status ($H = 3.2325$, $p = 0.5515$), educational attainment ($F = 7.288$, $p = 0.1872$), and number of years working in the organization ($H = 6.1444$, $p = 0.1048$) show no significant difference, as their p-values are greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted for these variables, indicating that work motivation does not significantly differ according to gender, marital status, educational attainment, and length of service. These findings suggest that personal demographic characteristics have minimal influence on employees' motivation compared to organizational and employment-related factors.

The findings indicate that age, tenure status, and position significantly influence employees' work motivation, while gender, marital status, educational attainment, and number of years working in the organization do not significantly affect motivation levels. This highlights the importance of organizational roles, employment security, and employees' stage in life in shaping work motivation among fast-food employees. This finding is supported by Almirante et al. (2025), who emphasized that work motivation among service-sector employees is significantly affected by employment-related factors such as tenure, job position, and organizational conditions. Similarly, Nuñez and Guballo (2025) noted that employees' motivation is more strongly influenced by workplace experiences, job responsibilities, and organizational support than by demographic characteristics. Their studies further emphasized that enhancing workplace conditions, employee recognition, and career opportunities can significantly improve employees' motivation and engagement in the fast-food industry.

Table 7

Test of Significant Difference on the Level of Work–Life Balance Among Employees of Fast-Food Establishments in Dipolog City When Analyzed According to Profile Variables

Profile Variables	Test Statistic	Computed Value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Age	F-value	2.4406	0.4861	Accept Ho	No Significant Difference
Gender	U-value	4232	0.08148	Accept Ho	No Significant Difference
Marital Status	H-value	2.1290	0.3449	Accept Ho	No Significant Difference

Profile Variables	Test Statistic	Computed Value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Educational Attainment	F-value	2.6637	0.6156	Accept Ho	No Significant Difference
Tenure Status	H-value	8.1010	0.01741	Reject Ho	Significant Difference
Position	H-value	2.1998	0.3329	Accept Ho	No Significant Difference
Number of Years Working in the Organization	H-value	4.3441	0.2266	Accept Ho	No Significant Difference

Note. Significant at 0.05 level of significance. If p-value is less than 0.05, reject Ho; if p-value is greater than 0.05, accept Ho.

Table 7 presents the test of significant difference on the level of work–life balance among employees of fast-food establishments in Dipolog City when analyzed according to their profile variables. The results reveal that tenure status has a significant difference in work–life balance, as indicated by an H-value of 8.1010 and a p-value of 0.01741, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. This led to the rejection of the null hypothesis, implying that employees’ work–life balance varies according to their employment status. This suggests that the nature and stability of employment influence employees’ ability to balance work responsibilities and personal life.

On the other hand, age ($F = 2.4406$, $p = 0.4861$), gender ($U = 4232$, $p = 0.08148$), marital status ($H = 2.1290$, $p = 0.3449$), educational attainment ($F = 2.6637$, $p = 0.6156$), position ($H = 2.1998$, $p = 0.3329$), and number of years working in the organization ($H = 4.3441$, $p = 0.2266$) all showed no significant difference, as their p-values are greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted for these variables, indicating that work–life balance does not significantly differ based on age, gender, marital status, educational attainment, position, and length of service. These findings imply that most demographic and job-related variables do not substantially affect employees’ work–life balance in the fast-food industry.

The findings suggest that tenure status is the only factor that significantly influences employees’ work–life balance, while other profile variables have no significant effect. This highlights that employment conditions, particularly job stability and employment arrangements, play an important role in shaping employees’ ability to manage work and personal responsibilities. This finding is supported by Tulliao (2025) and Naig and Borbon (2021), who emphasized that employment conditions—especially tenure and job stability—are major determinants of work–life balance, whereas demographic characteristics often have minimal influence. Their studies further revealed that greater job security and familiarity with work demands contribute to better work–life balance. Moreover, they noted that work–life balance is more strongly affected by job demands, employment arrangements, and workplace conditions than by personal characteristics. These findings reinforce the importance of improving employment

stability, workplace support, and organizational policies to enhance employees' work-life balance in the fast-food industry.

Table 8

Test of Significant Relationship Among Job Satisfaction, Work Commitment, and Work-Life Balance Among Employees of Fast Food Establishments in Dipolog City

Variables Compared	Rs Value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Job Satisfaction and Work Commitment	0.8058	0.0000	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship; Large Positive Correlation
Work Commitment and Work-Life Balance	0.2859	0.0000339	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship; Small Positive Correlation
Work-Life Balance and Job Satisfaction	0.3131	0.00000513	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship; Medium Positive Correlation

Note. Rs = Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient. Significant at 0.05 level of significance. If *p*-value is less than 0.05, reject Ho; if *p*-value is greater than 0.05, accept Ho.

Table 8 presents the test of significant relationship among job satisfaction, work commitment, and work-life balance among employees of fast-food establishments in Dipolog City. The results reveal that job satisfaction and work commitment have an Rs value of 0.8058 with a *p*-value of 0.0000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The findings indicate a significant relationship with a large positive correlation between job satisfaction and work commitment. This means that as employees' job satisfaction increases, their level of work commitment also increases. Conversely, lower levels of satisfaction may correspond to lower levels of commitment. Thus, the results suggest that job satisfaction is a strong predictor of employees' commitment in the fast-food industry. Employees who are satisfied with their work, particularly in terms of compensation, interpersonal relationships, and growth opportunities, are more likely to develop stronger emotional attachment, loyalty, and willingness to remain in the organization.

Furthermore, work commitment and work-life balance obtained an Rs value of 0.2859 with a *p*-value of 0.0000339, which is also less than the 0.05 level of significance. This led to the rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating a significant relationship with a small positive correlation between work commitment and work-life balance. The findings imply that as employees' work-life balance improves, their level of work commitment also tends to increase, although the strength of the relationship is relatively weak. This suggests that work-life balance contributes to employees' commitment, but it is only one of several influencing factors. While balancing work and personal responsibilities can enhance employees' willingness to stay and perform in the organization, other factors such as job satisfaction, compensation, and organizational support may exert a stronger influence on commitment levels.

Likewise, work–life balance and job satisfaction revealed an R_s value of 0.3131 with a p -value of 0.00000513, which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating a significant relationship with a medium positive correlation between work–life balance and job satisfaction. This implies that as employees' work–life balance improves, their level of job satisfaction also tends to increase. Conversely, poor work–life balance may result in lower satisfaction levels. The findings suggest that employees who are able to effectively manage their work and personal responsibilities are more likely to feel satisfied with their jobs. This highlights the importance of implementing supportive workplace practices such as flexible scheduling, manageable workloads, and employee wellness programs to enhance both work–life balance and job satisfaction.

The findings indicate that job satisfaction, work commitment, and work–life balance are significantly related to one another. Among the variables, job satisfaction and work commitment demonstrated the strongest relationship, indicating that satisfaction plays a major role in enhancing employees' commitment to the organization. Meanwhile, work–life balance also contributes positively to both commitment and satisfaction, although with weaker correlations. These findings emphasize the importance of improving workplace conditions, organizational support, and employee well-being programs to strengthen employee satisfaction, commitment, and overall organizational performance in the fast-food industry.

Conclusions

The findings of the study yield several important conclusions. The fast-food workforce in Dipolog City is predominantly composed of young, early-career employees occupying rank-and-file positions, underscoring the entry-level and labor-intensive nature of the industry. Employees are generally satisfied with their jobs, particularly in terms of interpersonal relationships and workplace support, while growth and development opportunities remain the least emphasized dimension. In terms of work commitment, employees exhibit a moderate level, with affective commitment emerging as the strongest component, suggesting that emotional attachment plays a significant role in their connection to the organization.

Moreover, employees experience a moderate level of work-life imbalance, wherein job demands and family responsibilities tend to interfere with one another, making it difficult to maintain clear boundaries between work and personal life. The results further indicate that job satisfaction and work motivation are significantly influenced by work-related factors such as age, tenure status, position, and length of service, whereas personal demographic variables do not significantly affect these outcomes. In contrast, work-life balance is significantly influenced only by tenure status, highlighting the importance of employment stability in enabling employees to better manage their work and personal responsibilities.

Furthermore, the study establishes a strong positive relationship between job satisfaction and work commitment, indicating that increased satisfaction leads to higher levels of commitment. It also reveals a moderate positive relationship between work-life balance and job satisfaction, as well as a weak but significant relationship between work-life balance and work commitment. Thus, the findings emphasize that organizational and work-related factors, such as job roles, tenure, compensation, and workplace environment, play a more critical role than personal demographic characteristics in shaping employees' job satisfaction, work commitment, and work-life balance in the fast-food industry.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, several recommendations are proposed to enhance employee well-being and organizational effectiveness within the fast-food sector. First, fast-food establishment owners and managers are encouraged to improve compensation structures by providing competitive salaries, fair allowances, and performance-based incentives, while ensuring equitable access to benefits and promoting job security through transparent employment and promotion practices. In addition, management should strengthen professional development initiatives by offering regular training, seminars, and clear career advancement pathways to address gaps in growth-related satisfaction and support long-term employee development.

Furthermore, organizations should cultivate a supportive and inclusive work environment by promoting teamwork, open communication, and consistent recognition programs. Efforts to enhance employee engagement and belongingness—such as team-building activities and supportive leadership practices—are essential in fostering stronger organizational commitment. Equally important is the implementation of employee-centered policies, including flexible scheduling, reasonable workloads, and wellness programs, to reduce stress and mitigate work-life conflict, thereby improving overall employee well-being.

At the institutional level, Local Government Units (LGUs), in partnership with private establishments, should reinforce labor standards, promote employee welfare, and support skills development initiatives. Collaboration with the Philippine National Police (PNP) and barangay officials should also be sustained to ensure safe and secure working environments, particularly for employees assigned to extended or shifting schedules. Moreover, management should establish systematic feedback mechanisms to regularly assess employee needs, monitor satisfaction levels, and guide continuous improvements in workplace policies and practices.

Finally, future researchers are encouraged to broaden the scope of inquiry by incorporating additional variables such as leadership style, organizational culture, and employee performance. Replication of the study across different locations and industries is likewise recommended to validate the findings and contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of workforce dynamics in diverse organizational contexts.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study strictly adhered to established ethical principles governing research involving human participants. Prior to data collection, formal permission was obtained from the management of selected fast-food establishments to ensure transparency and institutional compliance. Participation was entirely voluntary, and all respondents were fully informed of the study's purpose, procedures, and expected outcomes. Written informed consent was secured from each participant, affirming their willingness to participate and their right to withdraw at any stage without any form of penalty or disadvantage. Confidentiality and anonymity were rigorously maintained throughout the research process. No personally identifiable information was collected, and all responses were treated with strict confidentiality. The data gathered were used solely for academic purposes and were not disclosed to any third party, including employers, thereby safeguarding participants from any potential risks related to their employment or personal well-being.

The study ensured that no physical, psychological, or social harm was inflicted upon the participants. Data collection was conducted during respondents' free time or designated break periods to avoid disruption of their work responsibilities. All collected data were securely stored and remained accessible only to the researcher, and these were disposed of responsibly after the completion of the study in accordance with ethical data management standards. In addition, the study-maintained transparency in the use of technological tools. Artificial intelligence (AI) tools, such as QuillBot, were utilized solely for grammar checking and language refinement. These tools did not influence the research design, data collection, analysis, or interpretation of results. All intellectual content, analysis, and conclusions remain the original work of the researcher. Thus, the study upheld the fundamental ethical principles of respect for persons, beneficence, and justice, while ensuring academic integrity and responsible research practices throughout the entire process.

Acknowledgments

The researcher wishes to express profound and heartfelt gratitude to the thesis adviser, Michelle T. Baybay, for her unwavering guidance, invaluable insights, and steadfast support throughout the completion of this study. Her expertise and encouragement greatly contributed to the successful realization of this research.

Sincere appreciation is likewise extended to the panel members for their constructive comments, critical evaluations, and meaningful suggestions, which significantly enhanced the quality and rigor of this work.

The researcher also expresses deep gratitude to all respondents who generously shared their time, cooperation, and perspectives. Their participation played a vital role in the completion and credibility of this study.

Special thanks are given to the researcher's family for their constant encouragement, understanding, and moral support, which served as a source of strength and motivation throughout the research process.

Finally, the researcher extends sincere appreciation to all individuals who, in one way or another, contributed to the accomplishment of this study. Above all, the researcher offers utmost gratitude to God for His divine guidance, wisdom, and strength in making this endeavor possible.

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